

MEDICAL SCIENCES

DEPENDENCE OF THE QUALITY OF DENTURES ON THE TRANSFER OF PARAMETERS TO THE ARTICULATOR

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ABSTRACT

In the masticatory system, the lower jaw moves relative to the stationary upper jaw due to the functional activity of the joint, teeth and neuromuscular system. The main guiding component of the masticatory system is considered to be the temporomandibular joints (TMJ). To make dentures taking into account the characteristics of the TMJ and the movements of the lower jaw, a device is needed that can repeat the movement of the joint and the lower jaw.

Keywords: dentures, articulator, face bow.

In such a system, the chewing surfaces are modeled under constant control of simulating the movements of the lower jaw. Precise reproduction of each patient's individual mandibular movements optimizes the functional value of the manufactured dentures. The articulator's articular guide is mechanically reproduced using rectilinear track forms or a mechanical articulator fossa, in which the muscle functions in lateral movement are simulated by an adjustable Bennett angle.

The spatial position of the occlusal plane is an important landmark that determines the trajectory of movements, static and dynamic contacts. When moving from an anatomical system (patient) to a mechanical one (articulator), special attention should be paid to accurate registration and transfer of spatial parameters. It is possible to accurately reproduce the movements of the lower jaw in an articulator only if the jaw models cast in it are located in space relative to the articulator joints in the same way as the patient's dentition relative to the temporomandibular joint [1-3].

The purpose of our work was to determine the most rational way to transfer the parameters of the patients' dental system into the articulator and to comparatively assess the quality of manufactured dentures for various movements of the lower jaw. To achieve this goal, we set ourselves the following tasks: - selection of anatomical landmarks for transferring patient parameters to the articulator; - determination of the position of the jaws in the articulator space at individual and average values; - study of dynamic occlusion of patients for the presence of supercontacts.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We examined 39 patients with physiological types of occlusion and defects of the dentition in the lateral regions, aged 25-45 years, who were divided into 3 groups of 13 in each. The first group consisted of patients whose parameters of the dentofacial system were transferred using the traditional, arbitrary method. The 2nd group included patients whose parameters of the

dentofacial system were transferred according to average values using a setting key. The parameters of the dentofacial system of patients in group 3 were transferred to the articulator according to individual values using a face bow. In this work, we used a mid-anatomical articulator, with the help of which we studied diagnostic models, static and dynamic occlusions, and manufactured metal-ceramic bridges. The design of the articulator allows for hinged movements of the lower jaw, lateral, as well as forward and backward movements using a guide track that simulates the temporomandibular joint. The path of the joint is straight. The standard device has a Bonville triangle and an occlusal plane. The distance between the articular heads is 100 mm. It is possible to set the Bennett angle from 0° to 25°. The jaw models are held against each other by a vertical pin resting on the incisal rest. When moving the upper frame, the articular paths and the incisal stand are guide planes that set the paths of movement of the models or dentition against each other. To install the models into the articulator according to the average values, we used an installation key (balancer), with the help of which the models were accurately positioned and fixed at given points (landmarks). These points allow you to establish the position of the chewing plane. In this case, the incisive fork is installed in the transitional fold directly to the frenulum of the lower lip, and the sliding mechanism of the chewing plane is located at the level of half the height of the retromolar triangle or the distal buccal tubercle of the second lower molar. The orientation of the jaw models in the articulator space, similar to the position of the dentition in relation to the TMJ, was carried out using a face bow. The bite fork was secured to the upper dentition using thermoplastic mass or Zetaplus silicone material. The facebow was connected to the bite fork and adapter. The facebow was removed from the patient and disconnected from the adapter and bite fork.

RESULTS AND ITS DISCUSSION

As a result of the study with subsequent prosthetic replacement of dentition defects in patients in group 1, multiple occlusal contacts were obtained during contraction of the muscles that elevate the mandible. However, during the transition from a static mandibular position to a dynamic occlusion, supercontacts were detected. Thus, in 7 (17.9%) patients supercontacts were observed during protrusive movement of the lower jaw. In 10 (25.6%) patients, supercontacts occurred during lateral movement of the lower jaw on the working and balancing sides (working and balancing supercontacts, respectively). Patients of group 2, in the presence of multiple fissure-tubercle contacts in static conditions, had single supercontacts on the balancing side (balancing supercontacts). In 5 (12.8%) patients, undesirable "group management" was revealed on the working side, but this is considered to be a variant of the norm. Patients of group 3 with stable central occlusion had optimal characteristics of dynamic occlusion. Only in 1 (2.56%) patient was supercontact observed in the premolar area on the balancing side, which did not interfere with the free movement of the lower jaw (balancing supercontact). There were no supercontacts on the working side. The presence of supercontacts led to changes in the spatial position of the lower jaw, it was

difficult for patients to adapt to dentures, and there were complaints of tension in soft tissues, including mastication, and facial muscles. The elimination of supercontacts was carried out by grinding them off, which caused disruption of the occlusal surface of dentures, changing not only the aesthetic parameters, but also the functional characteristics of orthopedic structures.

Conclusion.

Thus, determining the true position of the occlusal plane relative to the temporomandibular joint makes it possible to reproduce the patient's individual parameters and control the function of the masticatory system at all stages of examination and treatment using the prosthetic method.

References

1. Abakarov S.I., Svirin V.V., Saperova N.R. i dr. Izuchenie modelej cheljustej v stomatologii. - M., 2008. -C. 301-303.
2. Hvatova V.A. Funkcional'naja diagnostika i lechenie v stomatologii. Klinicheskaja gnatologija. Sb., posv. 5-letiju obrazovanija sekcii. - M., 2007.- C. 61-62.
3. Gross M.D., Mathews J.D. Occlusion in Restorative Dentistry. - Churchill Livingstone, Edinburgh, Melbourne and New York, 1982. -P.218-220.